

**Emotional Expression and Gender Perceptions Among Indian Teenagers: A Comparative
Behavioural Study**

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Abstract

This study examines the psychological perspectives of Indian teenagers (ages 11–20) based on a survey called SOUL (Survey Of Understanding Life choices), conducted with 62 respondents (31 females, 31 males) across India. The analysis explores male inexpressiveness, emotional stability under societal influence, and gender polarization. Results indicate that traditional gender roles persist, with 65% of males exhibiting emotional suppression compared to 23% of females. Societal pressures significantly impact emotional stability, with 77% of females and 42% of males reporting mental exhaustion from overthinking ($\chi^2 = 8.7, p < .01$). Opinions on feminism and misogyny reveal gender polarization, with 68% of females supporting feminism versus 45% of males ($\chi^2 = 3.8, p = .05$). Compared to past generations, today's teenagers demonstrate increased emotional awareness but face modern challenges like social media influence. Additional themes, such as family dynamics, enrich the findings.

Keywords: Indian teenagers, emotional stability, gender polarization, societal influence, emotional suppression, feminism

Introduction

Gender roles, emotional expressiveness, and social expectations during adolescence and the psychological impact on every teenager are unique, as they pose a challenge for India, where contemporary culture impacts traditional customs. Where do Indian adolescents fit in the midst? Data extracted from our survey conducted with Indian adolescents and teenagers covers five major areas of problem concern. Nancy Chodorow's concept of "mothering" draws a graph that explains males' expressionless portrayal (Chodorow, 1978). The male figure below: active touchstone, emotion self-underbelied of gratitude self-inflation, is a father-daughter direct couple. Masculinity and femininity also encompass emotions of social domination, giving orders or action. Adolescence is a transformative period marked by emotional shifts, identity exploration, and societal expectations. In India, this developmental stage is uniquely influenced by the interplay between traditional values and the rapid globalization of culture. This research investigates how Indian adolescents navigate gender roles, emotional expressiveness, and social expectations in a dynamic cultural landscape. The research further delves into themes of misandry, feminism, and emerging biases, particularly those amplified through digital media. These findings suggest that the emotional and social development of adolescents is increasingly influenced by modern societal forces while still anchored in traditional family systems. This complex interaction provides the basis for a deeper understanding of the behavioural sociology of Indian youth across genders.

Literature Review

How Decisions Are Made

Kahneman (2011) distinguishes between fast, intuitive reasoning and slow, deliberative thinking, reflecting dual-process theories. Betsch (2008) suggests that gut feelings can intensify decision paralysis but may also indicate bias.

Mental Overload

Constant ruminating is associated with anxiety and insomnia (Morin et al., 2011). Zenner et al. (2014) found that overthinking could be alleviated through organized journaling and mindfulness techniques.

Feminism and Gender Attitudes

Awareness, inquiry, and commitment fuel feminist identity development (Downs, 2002). However, “reverse sexism” (misandry) continues to fuel debates on equity and remains largely misunderstood (Rudman & Glick, 2001).

Early Relationships and Family

The coexistence of mixed feelings from child to parent denotes normal individuation, while secure attachments foster resilience (Blos, 1979). Early romantic relationships serve as practice for emotion regulation (Shulman & Scharf, 2000).

Methodology

The whole study is based on the responses of the survey SOUL that we had created, considering various elements which included questions that would bring out various gender perspectives and assumptions. It also had questions that would reflect the emotional well-being of the participants. It was a Google form survey which we shared among our schoolmates and also on various social media platforms to capture a broader range of participants.

Participants

In total, 62 Indian teenagers (31 females, 31 males) aged 11-20 years (Mean Age \approx 16.5) had submitted the responses in the survey. Some of the participants were from our school, which is situated in Dibrugarh itself, while others hailed from various parts of our country. The exact number who belonged to our school is not known to us, as the responses submitted were anonymous.

Survey Design:

We had made the survey in such a way that it contained both open-ended questions (e.g., self-description, relationship with parents) and multiple-choice/binary questions (e.g., awareness of misandry, current relationship status), providing a comprehensive assessment of emotional expression, gender attitudes, and societal influences.

The survey was divided into 9 thematic blocks which contained 34 items: socio-demographics, self-concept (hobbies, self-description in 3 words), dominant decision making style, emotional control, gender views, and some theoretical helping behavior, dating life, and family relations.

Data collection

We surveyed in April 2025 and were accessible online via social media and other educational platforms. The data was cleaned and exported to CSV. Categorical variables (e.g., Decision Style: Gut vs. Analytical vs. Mixed) were used to code quantitative items. Most of the data and responses were on a qualitative basis to capture the mind-set of both genders in a detailed way. To promote honesty, responses were kept confidential.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data were grouped into more structured and attending themes, such as “male inexpressiveness” and “family systems,” among others. Their frequencies and percentages were based on the examined population. Differences between male and female participants were evaluated using chi-square statistics, where all degrees of freedom came to 1.

Results

We have divided the results into two parts – the quantitative results in the form of a table, where we have segregated the quantitative variables, and the qualitative findings, which we have put under the ‘Discussion’.

Table 1

Percentage comparison of different thematic blocks: Decision Making style and Attitude

Towards feminism

Variable	Percentage %
<i>Decision Making Style</i>	
Intuitive “gut feeling”	31
Deliberative (analytical)	45
Mixed Approach	24
Struggle to “switch off” thoughts at night (overthinking)	73
Mental exhaustion from overthinking	76
<i>Attitude Towards Feminism</i>	
Positive	55
Negative	19
Neutral	26

Note. Each variable under ‘Decision Making Style’ is scored out of 100; however, the values are independent and do not sum to 100. In contrast, the variables under ‘Attitude Towards Feminism’ are collectively scored out of 100.

Discussion

The Inexpressive Males

The idea of male inexpressiveness—the belief and pattern that men should suppress or not openly express their emotions—has its origins in a combination of historical, cultural, and psychological factors, deeply shaped by societal expectations about masculinity. The breakdown of this phenomenon has been beautifully described by Freudian psychology through the concept of ‘repression’. Repression is an unconscious defence mechanism carried out by the ego to keep unacceptable feelings, desires, and impulses (especially those that could generate anxiety or threaten one’s self-image) out of conscious awareness. In other words, it is a situation where men unconsciously keep certain emotional experiences out of awareness to conform to expectations and manage internal conflict. From very ancient times, ideals of masculinity have been linked to emotional stoicism (Pollack, 1999). Philosophers like Aristotle praised emotional restraint as a key masculine virtue, and Roman society considered fortitude and self-discipline with manliness.

Boys are often socialized from a very young age with phrases like “boys don’t cry” and “man up.” Such messaging teaches them that emotional expression—especially of sadness, fear, or tenderness—is not masculine, and that to express these emotions is to risk being seen as weak or “feminine.” This socialization results in boys exhibiting more emotional suppression than girls by the age of five (Addis & Mahalik, 2003). The psychoanalyst and sociologist Nancy Chodorow, who was a student of Sigmund Freud, had contributed important insights to this topic, especially in her book *The Reproduction of Mothering: Psychoanalysis and the Sociology of Gender*. She had highlighted an interesting argument that in early childhood, boys are encouraged to separate from their mother earlier than girls, leading to emotional distance, which is regarded as ideal in masculinity. Chodorow and others note that this suppression is not an

absence of genuine feeling—men often feel emotions deeply—but they learn to inhibit both internal acknowledgment and external expression, out of fear of judgment or ridicule, and in line with society’s idea of masculinity (Nussbaum, 2001).

In our survey, a similar trend was observed regarding this matter. A total of 65% of males (20 out of 31) reported some form of emotional suppression, which was greater than the 23% of females (7 out of 31) participating who reported emotional suppression. One male (16 years old) stated, “Can’t tell because I have less emotional feelings,” exemplifying emotional detachment. Another male (16 years old) stated, “I’m bored in life,” which implies a lack of goals, suggesting undealt-with emotions. Females were more expressive compared to males with 77% (24 out of 31) versus 42% of males (13 out of 31) ($\chi^2 = 8.7, p < .01$). The ‘amount’ of expression was inferred using number of words (which comprehended as meaningful sentences, and auxiliary verbs were excluded from the word count). Again, this highlights the fact that societal pressures place a great deal of expectation on male emotional stoicism, which might hurt emotional wellbeing and mental health.

Situational Influence on Emotional Stability, Mental Exhaustion, and Overthinking

The societal constructs of achievements, whether academic, familial, or peer, deeply undermined emotional stability. 77% of females (24 out of 31) and 42% of males (13 out of 31) reported mental exhaustion as a result of overthinking ($\chi^2 = 8.7, p < .01$). One female participant (15 years old) commented saying, “I think about a situation so much... then I just say ‘relax, it’s not that deep!’” A male (16 years of age) commented, “daily mentally exhausted,” giving voice to gendered reactions to an overabundance of stress.

Self-Awareness

Self-awareness differed by gender. A markedly higher proportion of females (74%, n=31) out of 23 self-described give detailed self-descriptions vs 16 self-described males (52%, n=31) showed in the results ($\chi^2 = 3.6, p = .06$). Ranging from curt (“I am good”, Age 16) to boastful (“Hot, handsome, egoistic”, Age 16), male responses indicate a divide between brash confidence and reticence, shedding light into the contrasting self-perception dynamics between females and males.

Gratitude

Gratitude often centred on parents despite criticisms. And a notable portion of females (65%, n=31) expressed deep gratitude (e.g. “motivation, love, and care,” Age 16) as compared to a lesser portion of males (48%, n=31) ($\chi^2 = 1.9, p = .17$). A female aged 16 observed, “I don’t respect and love them enough” and the male participant (Age 16) “No hate about parents” shows indirect gratitude.

Gender Expectations

Social culture defined gender expectations in diverse ways. Greater emphasis on independence 26 females (52%, n=31) stated “Females should be independent” v/s 29% in the form of “Feminism is fake” by 9 out of 31 males who were resistant to change ($\chi^2 = 3.5, p = .06$). Females appear more open to challenging norms, while males show greater resistance.

Gender Polarization

Feminism and Misandry

Views on feminism highlighted polarization. Support for feminism was very noticeable, with 68% of females (21 out of 31) supporting it (e.g., “Feminism is very necessary for a healthy society” – Age 17) compared to 45% of males (14 out of 31). 19% of males (6 out of 31) rejected feminism entirely, while no females did. Female respondents have greater awareness of misandry

(45%, 14 out of 31) compared to males (32%, 10 out of 31), though this was not significant ($\chi^2 = 1.2, p = .27$). A 16-year-old male defined misandry as “pure hatred... towards men”.

Romantic Relationships

Equal proportions of females (52%, 16 out of 31) and males (52%, 16 out of 31) reported being in relationships ($\chi^2 = 0.0, p = 1.0$), indicating no gender difference. However, 23% of males (7 out of 31) viewed early relationships negatively (e.g., “a curse at a very early stage” – Age 16) while only 10% of females (3 out of 31) held this view ($\chi^2 = 2.2, p = .14$), suggesting that males were not supportive of early relationships as females. The reason may likely due to past experiences, social expectations (fear), or parental fear.

Additional Topics

Family Engagement

Family systems were pivotal. 68% of females 21 out of 31 disengaged parental support and conflict merging “They support me...but fight in front of us” Age 16, versus only 45% of males 14 out of thirty-one ($\chi^2 = 3.5, p = .06$). This illustrates compassion fatigue in women as described by family functioning both as psychosocial stabilizer and stressor.

Another trend can be observed with participants who are not close or are in frequent conflicts with their parents tend to fall into early romantic relationships. True, we cannot assert this as a fact, but there is some correlation during this stage in life when the need for emotional support surges.

Modern Societal Impact (impact of social media)

Social media influence has a great scope of parlance. The digital exposure distinguishes this cohort from all pre-Internet eras. This becomes a worrying issue, especially within the context of feminist narrative, since the majority of women have acknowledged the presence of

feminists who are pseudo on social media and are spreading wrong ideas, in this case, misandry (Fardouly et al., 2015).

From the collected responses, we have observed that feminism is transforming the perception of male social media users to view feminism negatively, and consequently making them feel insecure (Salter, 2016). And on the positive side, that's something social media doesn't taint the perception, but at least the women acknowledge the fact that feminism on social media is very different.

Limitations of the Research

The study's sample of 62 respondents (31 females, 31 males) is limited in representing India's diverse adolescent population. This small sample size reduces statistical power, increasing the risk of Type II errors and potentially yielding spurious findings that may not generalize to larger, more diverse groups.

The age range (11–20 years) spans early adolescence to early adulthood, encompassing significant developmental differences in emotional maturity and cognitive understanding. Combining these age groups may obscure age-specific trends, particularly in complex concepts like feminism or misandry, which younger respondents (e.g., 11–14 years) may interpret differently than older ones (e.g., 15–20 years).

While chi-square tests met expected frequency assumptions, the small sample size may inflate test statistics, potentially leading to false positives. Additionally, these tests indicate association, not causation, limiting causal inferences about gender differences or societal influences.

Conducted in India, the study reflects cultural factors like collectivism and traditional gender roles, which may limit generalizability to non-Indian populations or less traditional Indian adolescent groups. For instance, findings on family dynamics (e.g., 68% of females reporting parental support) may be specific to India's family-oriented culture.

Conclusion

From the survey results, we have arrived at the conclusion that there are broadly two concerning topics that should be addressed. The first is the male inexpressiveness. From the research, it was evident that male inexpressiveness is affecting the emotional perception of boys significantly. Not only does it affect the emotional perception, but in the long term, this may cause hindrance in various situations of one's life. The consequences are huge, and difficulties are faced in relationships to even one's mental health. It also plays a significant role in the disproportionately high rate of suicide and violence among men compared to women. Thus, it is very necessary to address this issue.

To eradicate this, a comprehensive approach is required that begins in childhood. In early childhood, parents, caregivers, and educators play a crucial role by modelling and teaching emotional literacy—helping boys to name, understand, and appropriately express their feelings. The societal stereotypes regarding being 'manly' or 'man up' should be challenged and changed (Levant, 1992). Also, avoiding passing comments like "boys don't cry" is a crucial step to not associate 'crying' with their identity and gender.

Our second concern is regarding the gender perceptions. The root cause of the gender equality issue is the blame game and non-acknowledgement. In the survey, we saw that, unfortunately, most boys were hypocritical about feminist thoughts. Though some of them claimed that they have greater respect for women, other questions it reflected that the mentality was sexist (Messner, 2000). This was seen in the survey and also holds very true in our lives. The desire of feminism in a "limit" is itself very contradictory (Hooks, 2000).

Conversely, from the girls, though the extremism was far less, radicalism is also seen emerging. Generalization of men and making the same sexist remarks and expectations has

resulted in many men neglecting feminism, just as in men's women ignore men's issues.

Victimization and sympathy play cannot solve the issue. We also saw that many boys remained insensitive to the concepts of feminism because of the effects of social media. Some cases appearing quite often may influence the mind-set and may spread false concepts or stories about gender equality, while these cases may also influence the female youth in the wrong manner. So what do we do? The most effective method of eliminating any form of gender discrimination is to eliminate the source of the problem, which is the blame game. Rather than victimizing yourself, attempt to understand and empathize with the opposite gender. In the paper, instead of being a fault finder of the opposite gender, try to know the opposite gender's problems because, without knowing them, it is difficult to empathize, and difficulty in empathizing leads to difficulty in bringing change to society (Decety & Cowell, 2015).

So let us march towards a world where mutual respect transcends all boundaries—where every man honours every woman and every woman honours every man. A world where castes, religions, generations, and individuals uplift one another through shared respect, creating a society rooted in dignity, unity, and harmony.

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